

Composite Structures in Lightweight Photovoltaic Modules for Vehicle Integration

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Standard PV Module Assembly

Standard cells for standard modules

FRONT

BACK

Cell interconnection

- **Cells soldered in series connection** using ribbons going from the front to back of neighboring cells
- Ribbons: Cu core with SnPb(Ag) coating

- **Improve performance by** optimal number and size of busbars and ribbon are a shading vs. series loss trade-off

Soldering (tabbing) into strings (stringing)

Layup of strings and bussing

Encapsulant (EVA 450μm)

Glass

Bussing: large Cu tabs

→ 1 series connection of 60 cells

Module layup

Encapsulant
(EVA 450 μm)

Backsheet
PET/PVF/PA/Al/PVDF/...
or glass

Module lamination

Encapsulant cures or melts, layup becomes a module.

Motivation for lightweight modules

Reliability assessment of photovoltaics

- Hail impact testing
- Thermal cycling

Sample fabrication

Module exploded view

Sample fabrication

Fiber reinforced polypropylene backsheet

- Lamination of 8 plies
 - [0/90] unidirectional fibers
 - 60 w% glass fibers and 50 w% carbon fibers
- Glass and carbon fiber reinforcements

GFPP backsheet

CFPP backsheet

Fiber reinforced polymer backsheet $[0/90]_s$

Sample fabrication

Cell interconnection

- Cell interconnection foil
 - 18 Cu wires with SnBiAg-coating
 - Polyolefin-based carrier foil

Solar cell frontside

Connection foils

Sample fabrication

- Module layup and lamination
- During lamination:
 - Encapsulation
 - Soldering

Experimental matrix

	GFPP Backsheet	CFPP Backsheet
MW1 (PO)		
MW2 (PO + GF)		

- Thermal cycling according to IEC61215

Reliability assessment

Thermal cycling (-40 to 85 °C, IEC 61215)

Reliability assessment

Thermal cycling (-40 to 85 °C, IEC 61215)

3D Micro-computed tomography

- Non-destructive analyzing technique
- Multiple X-ray scans of rotating sample, followed by reconstruction to create 3D volume rendering
- Voxel (3D Pixel) sized as low as 1-3 μm
- Resolution depends on sample size

Reliability assessment and characterization

Micro-computed tomography (μ -CT) imaging

- Wire deformation between cells due to thermal strain

Reduced thermal strain

$$\Delta G = L \cdot \alpha_{backsheet} - C \cdot \alpha_{Si}$$

GFPP: $\Delta G = 7.5 \mu\text{m}/^\circ\text{C}$

CFPP: $\Delta G = 0.2 \mu\text{m}/^\circ\text{C}$

Conclusions

- Lightweight modules using a multi-wire interconnection are prone to degradation due to thermo-mechanical stress
- Decreasing the backsheet CTE improves the reliability
- Using carbon fibre reinforcement in a polymer backsheet increases module reliability
- Further investigation using FEM is ongoing

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Thanks for your attention!!

Questions
&
discussion